

1 **Sensory Cortical Mapping in Voluntary Awake and Unrestrained Sheep**

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16
17 **Abstract.** Sensory perception is central to how animals communicate and interact with their
18 environment. Insight into sensory processes is essential for understanding animal cognition and
19 improving their welfare^{1,2}. Using functional magnetic resonance imaging in voluntary awake and
20 unrestrained sheep, we noninvasively mapped brain regions involved in auditory and
21 somatosensory processing – two modalities crucial for social communication³. The auditory
22 cortex, located bilaterally in the ectosylvian gyrus, revealed evidence of tonotopy and voice
23 selectivity, with the dorsal posterior part emerging as a strong candidate for the primary auditory
24 cortex. Gentle back stroking induced activations in the anterior suprasylvian sulcus and other
25 somatosensory areas. These findings reveal the organization of sensory cortices in conscious
26 livestock and provide insight into the neural basis of their mental states. This approach paves the
27 way for investigating both normal and pathological sheep brain function with animals who have
28 the choice to participate or not. It also overturns long-standing stereotypes about sheep as passive
29 or cognitively limited animals, showing instead that they can voluntarily engage in complex
30 tasks.

31
32 **Main Text.** Sensory perception plays a fundamental role in how social animals perceive and
33 interact with their environment. In recent years, cognitive neuroscience has increasingly
34 emphasized the importance of understanding these sensory processes not only to explore animal
35 cognition but also to improve animal welfare by gaining insight into their mental states^{1,2}. Sheep,
36 as highly social animals, are emerging as a valuable large-animal model in neuroscience – now
37 being adopted by major neurotechnology and clinical research groups such as Neuralink and
38 Paradromics⁴. Existing evidence for sensory regions in the sheep brain is based on anesthetized
39 or postmortem studies⁴⁻⁸, leaving a key gap in understanding sensory processing in awake
40 animals. In addition, at a time when public and policymaker attitudes range from seeking a clear
41 justification for continued animal research to calling for its total abolition, the refinement of
42 experimental procedures to minimize physical and mental harm to animals should always be a
43 priority⁹. By providing access to the cognitive and emotional lives of sheep, awake and

44 unrestrained fMRI will enable the investigation of sensory processing in fully conscious,
45 voluntarily participating animals^{10,11}.

46

47 **The sheep auditory cortex**

48 We first mapped the sheep auditory cortex in animals trained (AW) for voluntary awake fMRI¹¹,
49 using pure-tone frequency¹² – AW-BIP – and complex sounds¹³ – AW-SVL – paradigms with
50 continuous temporal sampling, and in anesthetized animals (AN) using pure-tone paradigm with
51 either continuous – AN-BIP-Continuous – or sparse¹⁴ – AN-BIP-Sparse – temporal sampling
52 (Supplementary Table 1, see methods). All experiments contrasted sound stimulations with a
53 non-stimulation baseline, and consistently revealed significant activations in the anterior part of
54 the posterior ectosylvian gyrus, the putative auditory cortex^{4,5}. In awake sheep, the five animals
55 that completed both experiments (BIP & SVL) had significant bilateral activations to sound in
56 the ectosylvian gyrus, except one (Lily, AW-BIP), who showed right-hemisphere-only
57 activations (at least $p < 0.001$, uncorrected, and certain family-wise error (FWE), corrected; Fig.
58 1; Supplementary Tables 3-12). Posterior ectosylvian activations in response to BIP were
59 bilateral in two animals (Barnita, Léonard) or in the right hemisphere (Lily, Maggie, Ted), and
60 bilateral for all animals in AW-SVL, except one (Barnita), who showed left-hemisphere-only
61 activation. Additional significant activations in the anterior ectosylvian gyrus were found in all
62 animals for AW-BIP (bilateral: Léonard; right: Barnita, Lily; left: Maggie, Ted) and bilaterally in
63 three out of these five animals (Barnita, Léonard, Lily) for AW-SVL. A sixth sheep (Brook)
64 achieved the AW-BIP experiment but had no activation in the ectosylvian gyrus (Supplementary
65 Tables 1, 13). Subcortical activations in the medial geniculate nucleus were detected in two
66 animals (left: Léonard, right: Maggie; at least $p < 0.001$, uncorrected; Supplementary Tables 9,
67 11) in the AW-SVL experiment. Under anesthesia, all four animals had significant activations in
68 the ectosylvian gyrus in AN-BIP-Continuous (at least $p < 0.001$, uncorrected; Fig. 1;
69 Supplementary Tables 14-17), while three out of these four in AN-BIP-sparse (at least $p < 0.001$,
70 uncorrected, and one voxel FWE, corrected; Fig. 1; Supplementary Tables 18-20). As with
71 awake sheep, significant activations were found in the posterior and in the anterior ectosylvian
72 gyrus. Subcortical activations were detected in the left medial geniculate nucleus (AN-BIP-
73 Continuous: 03686; AN-BIP-Sparse: 03068; at least $p < 0.001$, uncorrected; Supplementary
74 Tables 17, 20). In both awake and anesthetized experiments, activations outside the hypothesized
75 region were observed consistently across animals in the cerebellum and the cingulate gyrus (at
76 least $p < 0.001$, uncorrected, and certain FWE corrected, Supplementary Tables 3-20).
77 Overall, more and stronger activations to sound were observed in experiments with awake
78 animals than those under anesthesia. Thus, we statistically compared activations for AW-BIP
79 greater than AN-BIP. Within the right ectosylvian and surrounding posterior regions, AW-BIP
80 activations were stronger than AN-BIP-continuous ($p < 0.0001$, uncorrected; Supplementary Table
81 21) and AN-BIP-sparse ($p < 0.0001$, uncorrected; Supplementary Table 22). In addition, there was
82 some indication of more and stronger activations in the ectosylvian gyrus for AN-BIP-sparse
83 than for AN-BIP-continuous. Statistical comparison of AN-BIP-sparse and AN-BIP-continuous
84 showed some voxels within the ectosylvian gyrus activated more for AN-BIP-sparse, while
85 others showed the opposite effect (at least $p < 0.001$, uncorrected; Supplementary Tables 23-24).
86 Thus, there was no clear advantage of using sparse temporal sampling to localize the sheep
87 auditory cortex.

88

89

90 **Fig.1 | Localizing the sheep auditory cortex.** Axial (left) and frontal (right) views show
 91 activation within the ectosylvian gyrus across experiments AW-BIP (Léonard), AW-SVL (Lily),
 92 AN-BIP-Continuous (animal 03111), and AN-BIP-Sparse (animal 03068). Activation maps for
 93 the contrast sound > baseline are displayed using jet color scale thresholded at $p < 0.001$,
 94 uncorrected. The transparent red overlay represents the hypothesized region-of-interest.
 95 Crosshairs in the axial and frontal views indicate the same voxel.

96

97 Next, frequency selectivity was investigated using the pure-tone (BIP) paradigm with continuous
 98 temporal sampling in both awake and anesthetized sheep, and with sparse temporal sampling in
 99 anesthetized animals (Supplementary Tables 25-52). We observed limited but detectable
 100 evidence for tonotopic organization – defined as spatial gradient of frequency selectivity in
 101 which adjacent clusters of voxels show preferential BOLD responses to high or low
 102 frequencies^{15,16}. In the AW-BIP experiment, three sheep (Barnita, Lily, Ted) exhibited adjacent
 103 frequency-selective clusters (at least $p < 0.001$, uncorrected, and certain family-wise error (FWE),
 104 corrected; Supplementary Tables 25-30) within the left posterior ectosylvian gyrus. These
 105 clusters formed a low-to-high frequency gradient beginning at the dorsal aspect of the anterior
 106 part of the posterior ectosylvian gyrus (Fig. 2). Under anesthesia, one animal (03686) showed
 107 such clusters in the right posterior ectosylvian gyrus for AN-BIP-continuous, and bilaterally in

108 the posterior ectosylvian gyrus for AN-BIP-sparse (at least $p < 0.001$, uncorrected, Supplementary
 109 Tables 43-44, 51-52). Apart from these cases, frequency preference was generally restricted to
 110 isolated voxels without clear topographic arrangement.
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 113
 114 **Fig.2 | Evidence for tonotopic organization in the posterior ectosylvian gyrus.** *Left: AW-BIP,*
 115 *Barnita; Middle: AW-BIP, Lily; Right: AN-BIP-Continuous, 03686. Axial (top) and frontal*
 116 *(bottom) views are represented; activation maps are displayed using red to yellow color scale for*
 117 *the contrast High > Low, and blue to green color scale for the contrast Low > High both*
 118 *thresholded at $p < 0.001$, uncorrected.*

119
 120 We further investigated voice selectivity – defined as stronger responses to conspecific
 121 vocalizations than to heterospecific vocalizations and non-vocals sounds^{13,17-20} – using the
 122 complex sounds (SVL) paradigm with continuous temporal sampling in awake sheep (see
 123 methods). Sheep vocalizations reliably elicited larger BOLD responses than both non-sheep
 124 animal vocalizations and non-vocal environmental sounds in the anterior ectosylvian gyrus, with
 125 four out of five animals showing significant activations (at least $p < 0.001$, uncorrected;
 126 Supplementary Tables 53-56). Two distinct activation patterns were observed across animals. In
 127 two animals (Ted, Barnita), a single significant voxel ($p < 0.001$, uncorrected; Fig. 3;
 128 Supplementary Tables 53-54) was detected in the left anterior ectosylvian gyrus. In contrast, two
 129 other animals (Lily, Maggie) showed significant activation in the right anterior ectosylvian
 130 gyrus, accompanied by bilateral significant voxels (at least $p < 0.001$, uncorrected; Fig. 3;
 131 Supplementary Tables 55-56) in the posterior ectosylvian gyrus.

132

133 **Fig.3 | Evidence for voice-selective areas in the sheep auditory cortex.** *Frontal views show*
 134 *significant activations in the anterior ectosylvian gyrus (left hemisphere for Ted and Barnita,*
 135 *right hemisphere for Maggie and Lily) and in the posterior sylvian gyrus (bilateral for Maggie*
 136 *and Lily). Activation maps are displayed using jet color scale (blue to red) thresholded at*
 137 *$p < 0.001$, uncorrected, for the conjunction of sheep vocalizations > non-sheep vocalizations and*
 138 *sheep vocalizations > non-vocal environmental sounds. White triangles indicate aEG.*

139

140 **The sheep somatosensory cortex**

141 Finally, we mapped somatosensory responses to gentle tactile stimulation of the back²¹, in awake
 142 (AW-TOUCH) and anesthetized (AN-TOUCH) sheep (see methods), using continuous temporal
 143 sampling (Supplementary Tables 57-64). When contrasting tactile stimulations with a non-
 144 stimulation baseline, only three animals (AW: Léonard; AN: B02, B04) showed significant
 145 activations in the posterior part of the anterior suprasylvian sulcus (at least $p < 0.001$, uncorrected;
 146 Fig. 4; Supplementary Tables 57, 63, 64), the region hypothesized to respond to back stimulation
 147 in sheep⁶⁻⁸. In AW-TOUCH, additional activations were observed in other putative
 148 somatosensory regions (at least $p < 0.001$, uncorrected; Supplementary Tables 57-60). Two
 149 animals (Ted, Maggie) showed significant activations in the anterior sigmoideus gyrus,
 150 classically identified as primary somatosensory cortex (SI) in sheep⁸. All but Maggie had
 151 significant activations in the postcruciate gyrus, described as SI in other mammals²¹. All sheep
 152 also showed significant activations in the orbitofrontal gyrus, previously reported to display
 153 sensory responsiveness⁸. Under anesthesia, all sheep had significant activations in the anterior
 154 sigmoideus gyrus (at least $p < 0.001$, uncorrected; Supplementary Tables 61-64). Orbitofrontal
 155 and postcruciate activations were found in all but B01 and B02, respectively (at least $p < 0.001$,
 156 uncorrected; Supplementary Tables 61-64). In both awake and anesthetized sheep, additional
 157 activations outside the somatosensory regions were consistently found in the cerebellum, as well
 158 as in the cingulate, suprasylvian and precruciate gyri (at least $p < 0.001$, uncorrected;
 159 Supplementary Tables 57-64).

160 Statistical comparison between physiological states (AW & AN) revealed no significant
 161 difference in any hypothesized region. In the right precruciate gyrus, some voxels had higher
 162 responses to AW-TOUCH (FWE, corrected; Supplementary Table 65), whereas others to AN-

163 TOUCH (FWE, corrected; Supplementary Table 66). The suprasylvian gyrus and cerebellum
164 showed greater responses during AW-TOUCH (FWE, corrected; Supplementary Table 65),
165 whereas the bilateral cingulate responded more during AN-TOUCH (FWE, corrected;
166 Supplementary Table 66).

167
168 **Fig.4 | Localizing the sheep somatosensory cortex.** *Frontal views show activations within the*
169 *posterior part of the anterior suprasylvian sulcus (transparent purple overlay) across*
170 *experiments AW-TOUCH (Léonard) and AN-TOUCH (B02, B04). Activation maps for the*
171 *contrast touch > baseline are displayed using jet color scale (blue to red) thresholded at*
172 *p<0.001, uncorrected.*

173
174 Processing of back touching was expected to occur in the contralateral posterior part of the
175 anterior suprasylvian sulcus to the touched flank^{8,22}. However, when comparing left-greater-than-
176 right and right-greater-than-left contrasts in both awake and anesthetized sheep, there was no
177 clear evidence of contralateral processing in this region (Supplementary Tables 67-82). One
178 anesthetized sheep (B01) even displayed ipsilateral processing in this region (p<0.001,
179 uncorrected; Supplementary Tables 71, 79). Another indication of ipsilateral processing was
180 observed in the anterior sigmoideus gyrus (predicted SI). In the left-greater-than-right contrast,
181 the left SI was consistently activated in both awake and anesthetized animals (except B04; at

182 least $p < 0.001$, uncorrected; Supplementary Tables 67-73). In contrast, right SI activation in the
183 right-greater-than-left contrast was less consistent, observed only in three animals (AW:
184 Léonard; AN: B01, B03; Supplementary Tables 75, 79, 81).

185

186 **Discussion**

187 In this study, we demonstrate the feasibility of performing fMRI with awake and unrestrained
188 sheep – a methodological advance that enables the investigation of sensory processing in fully
189 conscious, voluntarily participating animals¹¹. Using this approach, we mapped brain regions
190 involved in auditory and somatosensory processing, two key modalities essential for social
191 communication³.

192 Our results delineate the sheep auditory cortex within the posterior ectosylvian gyrus, confirming
193 its localization as previously defined by neuronal tracing⁵, but also reveal additional activations
194 in the anterior ectosylvian gyrus, suggesting a broader extent of this cortical sensory region. In
195 awake sheep, we found functional evidence for tonotopic organization within the posterior
196 ectosylvian gyrus, a defining feature of mammalian auditory cortex²³. Although limited, the
197 organization we observe is consistent with patterns in cats and dogs, where a low-to-high
198 frequency gradient originates dorsally in this region^{16,24}. A recent anatomical study described a
199 dorsoventral gradient of parvalbumin expression in the posterior ectosylvian gyrus, with higher
200 densities dorsally²⁵. Because parvalbumin is an immunohistochemical marker for identifying
201 primary auditory areas²⁶, and tonotopy is a defining feature of these regions^{15,16}, the co-
202 occurrence of a dorsoventral parvalbumin gradient and corresponding tonotopic organization
203 supports the dorsal posterior ectosylvian gyrus as a strong candidate for the sheep primary
204 auditory cortex. Beyond tonotopic organization, we investigated cortical specialization for
205 conspecific vocalizations in awake sheep. We identified a putative voice patch in the anterior
206 ectosylvian gyrus, with a possible additional patch in the posterior ectosylvian gyrus. Voice
207 patches have been reported consistently in other species^{13,17–20}, although the precise location of
208 these patches varied between individuals^{19,20,27}. These results suggest that cortical specialization
209 for conspecific vocalizations may represent a neural mechanism conserved across social
210 mammals^{18–20,28}, reflecting an evolutionarily ancient substrate for vocal communication.

211 Our results also refine the organization of the sheep somatosensory cortex. Tactile stimulation of
212 the back induced activations in the posterior part of the anterior suprasylvian sulcus in three
213 animals, consistent with the location of the secondary somatosensory cortex previously defined
214 by retrograde tracing⁶ and microelectrode recordings⁸. Additionally, we observed activations in
215 the anterior sigmoideus gyrus, classically defined as SI^{6,8}, challenging earlier reports that
216 described SI as exclusively oro-facial^{6,8}. The presence of body-related responses in SI indicates
217 that the ovine somatosensory cortex follows the broader mammalian organization²², rather than
218 constituting an exception. Activations in the orbitofrontal gyrus are consistent with prior reports
219 of sensory responsiveness in this area⁶. Our results further align with an earlier fMRI study in
220 anesthetized sheep⁷, in which hind-leg stimulation activated a region that we interpret, based on
221 the authors' Fig. 1, as lying at the intersection of the posterior sigmoideus, postcruciate, anterior
222 suprasylvian, and ectolateral gyri. We identified activations in response to gentle back stroking
223 in each of these regions, suggesting that body representation extends across a distributed
224 somatosensory network²¹. However, it remains difficult to determine whether gentle back
225 stroking is processed contralaterally, ipsilaterally, or bilaterally in sheep.

226 Outside the hypothesized regions, cerebellar activations emerged consistently across both
227 auditory and tactile fMRI experiments. Although classically associated with motor coordination,
228 the cerebellum is known to participate in a range of sensorimotor and predictive processes^{29,30},
229 and cerebellar engagement during sensory stimulation has been reported in other species²¹. In the
230 tightly constrained scanning environment, sheep must actively maintain a learned, motionless
231 posture and inhibit orienting responses to tactile or auditory inputs; such task demands may
232 contribute to the cerebellar activity observed here²¹, although additional sensory or integrative
233 roles cannot be excluded. We also noted activation in the cingulate gyrus, a region implicated in
234 affective and attentional aspects of sensory processing³¹.

235 Comparisons between awake and anesthetized sheep revealed modality-specific effects, with
236 auditory responses particularly attenuated under anesthesia, even when sparse temporal sampling
237 was used to minimize scanner noise¹⁴. These differences underscore the importance of
238 preserving natural physiological states for accurate functional mapping and support the
239 development of animal welfare-friendly neuroimaging protocols that avoid the negative effects
240 of anesthetics³². Awake unrestrained fMRI in sheep thus provides a powerful foundation for
241 investigating higher-order sensory processing that cannot be accessed under anesthesia. This
242 opens new avenues for neuroscience, animal welfare, and translational research with sheep and
243 sets the challenge to determining which other species are capable of achieving this optimally
244 refined animal research approach.

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354

355 **Methods.**

356 **Experimental design**

357 Brain regions involved in auditory and somatosensory processing were investigated in both awake
358 unrestrained (AW), and in anesthetized (AN) sheep using fMRI. Three sensory stimulation
359 paradigms were conducted:

360 *BIP experiments.* A group of awake (AW-BIP) and a group of anesthetized (AN-BIP) sheep were
361 presented with pure-tone stimuli to map the auditory cortex and its potential tonotopic
362 organization¹².

363 SVL experiment. A sheepvoice localizer was used in awake sheep (AW-SVL) to map the auditory
364 cortex and identify voice-selective areas - regions that preferentially respond to conspecific
365 vocalizations compared to heterospecific vocalizations or non-vocals sounds¹³.

366 TOUCH experiments. Tactile stimulation of the back was applied to map the somatosensory cortex
367 in both awake and anesthetized groups (AW-TOUCH, AN-TOUCH).

368 All experiments were performed using continuous temporal sampling. Sparse temporal sampling
369 was additionally implemented for AN-BIP to reduce scanner acoustic noise during stimulus
370 presentation¹⁴, and to enable comparison of brain activations between sparse (AN-BIP-Sparse) and
371 continuous acquisitions (AN-BIP-Continuous).

372 An experimental session consisted of one or more consecutive fMRI runs. Each run contained one
373 or more trials, with a trial encompassing one block of each condition of the stimulation paradigm
374 and a baseline condition. The number of sessions, runs, and trials per run varied depending on the
375 individual and experiment (Extended Data Table 1). For all experiments, complete trials from a
376 run were analyzed if head movement was less than two millimeters.

377

378 **Animals.** A total of fifteen healthy Ile-de-France sheep (*Ovis aries*) participated in this fMRI
379 study (Extended Data Table 1). Eight performed fMRI under general anesthesia: four of them
380 completed the AN-BIP experiment (Continuous & Sparse), while the other four took part in AN-
381 TOUCH. Seven sheep achieved awake, unrestrained fMRI for the AW-BIP experiment.
382 However, as Tony completed only 27 trials and our minimum required number of trials was 40,
383 his data was not analyzed. Five sheep participated in AW-SVL, and four in AW-TOUCH. All
384 animals were bred and cared for at the Unité Expérimentale de Physiologie Animale de
385 l'Orfrière (<https://doi.org/10.15454/1.5573896321728955E12>). All procedures were performed
386 in accordance with the European directive 2010/63/EU on the protection of animals used for
387 scientific purposes and were approved by the local ethics committee (CEEA VdL, Tours, France,
388 authorization #26807-2020080314491255v6).

389

390 **Auditory stimulation paradigms.** All sound stimuli were presented using PsychoPy version
391 2022.2.4³³, controlled by a MacPro desktop computer. The stimuli were delivered through MR-
392 compatible headphones (MR Confon, Magdeburg, Germany) at a sound pressure level of
393 between 65-85 dB.

394 *AN-BIP & AW-BIP.* The same sound stimulation paradigm was used for both AN-BIP and AW-
395 BIP (supplementary file, broadband_continuous.psyexp). Sound stimulation blocks contained
396 either predominantly low- or predominantly high-frequency pure tones, and were created based

397 on the recommendations of Langers and colleagues¹². Frequencies ranged from 125 to 8000
398 Hertz, with low frequencies randomly selected from this range using a decreasing cumulative
399 probability distribution. Whereas, high frequencies were selected based on an increasing
400 cumulative probability distribution. Each block contained 88 tones of different frequencies. A
401 tone lasted 75 milliseconds, with a 25 millisecond gap between two tones. Total block duration
402 was 8800 ms. Sound block amplitude was ramped up linearly over the first second and ramped
403 down over the last second of a block.

404 A trial consisted of one block of each of three conditions - Low, High, Baseline - presented in a
405 pseudo-randomized order, ensuring that the same condition did not appear consecutively.

406 During the sparse and continuous AN-BIP experiments, each run consisted of 50 trials. The order
407 of the sparse and continuous acquisitions was counterbalanced across sheep: one male and one
408 female had the order Continuous-Sparse-Continuous-Sparse while the others had the order
409 Sparse-Continuous-Sparse-Continuous. Two runs of both Sparse and Continuous were acquired
410 within a session. The entire experimental session was repeated approximately four weeks later,
411 with the order of fMRI acquisitions reversed (i.e., those who started with Sparse in the first
412 session started with Continuous in the second, and vice versa). For each experiment, the total
413 number of analyzed trials can be found in Extended Data Table 1.

414 During each AW-BIP session, sheep performed between 1 and 5 consecutive runs (each
415 comprising 1 to 8 trials) and were rewarded after each run. The number of trials per run was
416 determined at the beginning of each run, based on the animal's recent behavior and performance.
417 The actual number of trials completed depended on the sheep's patience and ability to remain
418 motionless during the scan (Extended Data Table 1).

419 *AW-SVL*. Three auditory conditions were used in this experiment: non-sheep animal
420 vocalizations (NSV), sheep vocalizations (SV), non-vocal environment sounds (NV). For each
421 condition, 16 examples of sounds were selected. NSV and NV were collected from
422 <https://neuralbasesofcommunication.eu/download/>. SV were recorded with a Zoom F6
423 Multitrack Field Recorder from outdoor flocks of Ile-de-France ewes unknown to the sheep who
424 took part in the experiment. The sounds from all conditions were normalized to have the same
425 peak amplitude using the free software Audacity ® version 3.4.2
426 (<https://sourceforge.net/projects/audacity/>).

427 A block lasted 8000 milliseconds and contained seven individual sounds from a single category
428 (i.e., NSV, SV, NV). These seven individual sounds were randomly selected, without
429 replacement, from the 16 examples of each category condition. Each individual sound lasted
430 between 0.45 and 2.1 seconds (mean = 0.93 seconds; standard deviation = 0.37 seconds). The
431 amount of silence between two individual sounds (i.e., inter-stimulus-interval, ISI) was
432 calculated by subtracting the duration of the seven individual sounds from 8 seconds, and the
433 result divided by the number of ISI required in a block (i.e., 7). Thus, ISI duration differed across
434 blocks and was between 18 and 39 milliseconds.

435 A trial consisted of one block of each of the three auditory conditions (i.e., NSV, SV, NV) and a
436 baseline block. The order of block presentation was pseudo-randomized, with the first trial
437 always starting with a baseline block then, the other three conditions were played in random
438 order. After the first trial, the distribution of the four blocks within a trial was random, with the
439 constraint that two blocks of the same condition could not be presented successively across trials.
440 During AW-SVL sessions, a maximum of five consecutive runs was performed, each consisting

441 of up to three trials, which was determined before the start of each run. Sheep were rewarded
442 between each run.

443

444 **Tactile stimulation paradigm**

445 The same tactile stimulation paradigm was used for both AN-TOUCH and AW-TOUCH
446 (supplementary file, touch.psyexp). As sheep can have thick wool, a line was shaved on each
447 side of the spine, from the shoulder to the hip, to allow direct skin stimulation and provide
448 reference points for consistent stimulations across fMRI sessions. AN sheep were shaved on the
449 day of the experiment while AW sheep were regularly shaved since the acquisitions took place
450 over several months.

451 Tactile stimulations were performed on the right and left shaved lines based on the
452 recommendations of Guran and colleagues²¹. Stimulations consisted of gently stroking from the
453 shoulder to the hip using a wooden back scratcher (Extended Data Table 1). A tactile stimulation
454 block lasted for eight seconds and included two of these strokes (each lasting 3.5 seconds) on the
455 same side of the animal, separated by one second for the trainer to reposition the back scratcher
456 at the shoulder position. A trial consisted of three conditions - Right, Left, Baseline. Each trial
457 began with an eight second stimulation on a randomly chosen side (Left or Right) followed by an
458 eight second baseline block. Then the other side was stimulated in the same manner and followed
459 by a baseline block. AW-TOUCH consisted of 1 to 6 consecutive runs during an experimental
460 session, with a reward in between runs. Each run consisted of 1 to 3 trials; the number of trials
461 was determined before the start of each run. In AN-TOUCH, each animal completed two runs of
462 25 trials (Extended Data Table 1).

463 The trainer performing the tactile stimulations received auditory cues – inaudible to the sheep –
464 through MR-compatible headphones (MR Confon, Magdeburg, Germany) to indicate which side
465 of the animal to stroke and when to apply the stimulation - beeps were used to indicate the start,
466 middle and end of each stroking action. Standing at the front of the scanner, to the left side of the
467 scanner bed, the trainer used the back scratcher to stroke the sheep's back. For AN-TOUCH, two
468 trainers (CeP & SAL) performed tactile stimulations, each working with one ewe and one ram.
469 For AW-TOUCH, only one trainer (CeP) performed tactile stimulations with a second trainer
470 (CaP, DD or SAL) remaining at the back of the scanner, motionless and facing the sheep, to give
471 instructions between runs to the animal and the person starting the acquisition. In all TOUCH
472 experiments, an experimenter ensured that the trainer touched the correct side indicated by the
473 auditory cue - no mistakes were made.

474

475 **Anesthesia**

476 General anesthesia was used for the AN-BIP and AN-TOUCH experiments. To avoid the risks
477 associated with regurgitation during general anesthesia, sheep were fasted approximately 18
478 hours before. They were transported to the MRI platform the day before the experiment.
479 Anesthesia was induced by an intrajugular injection of CLORKETAM 1000 (ketamine 7-10
480 mg.kg⁻¹) and ROMPUN 2% (xylazine 0.05 mg.kg⁻¹). Animals were intubated (8.5 mm probe,
481 SON612, Centravet, France) and ventilated with an oxygen/air mix to enable an automatic
482 maintenance of respiration. A catheter was then placed in the jugular vein to maintain anesthesia
483 with a continuous infusion of ketamine and xylazine mix (10 mL ketamine and 2 mL xylazine
484 diluted in 500 mL of saline, 100 drops per minute). The duration of anesthesia was

485 approximately 1.5 hours, during which cardiac rhythm and SpO2 levels were continuously
486 monitored.

487

488 **Training protocol for awake unrestrained MRI acquisitions**

489 All seven AW sheep had previously completed an awake and unrestrained MRI training protocol
490 and had demonstrated the ability to remain motionless during training and MRI acquisitions. The
491 training procedure, based on positive reinforcement, has previously been described in detail¹¹.
492 Number and duration of MRI sessions, number of runs, and trials per run depended on the
493 sheep's patience and ability to stay motionless during the acquisition (milliseconds).

494 *AW-BIP & AW-SVL*: During training sessions in the MRI room, each sheep was presented with
495 blocks of sounds via MR compatible headphones (MR Confon, Magdeburg, Germany), without
496 an fMRI acquisition sequence. Once they were familiarized with the auditory stimuli, fMRI
497 acquisitions were also conducted.

498 *AW-TOUCH*: All training sessions took place in the MRI room, where sheep were familiarized
499 with being touched and stroked on their back. The trainer gradually introduced the wooden back
500 scratcher - first by touching one side, followed with a reward, then completing an entire trial
501 before rewarding the sheep. Once the sheep remained motionless during a trial, fMRI
502 acquisitions were conducted.

503

504 **MRI acquisitions**

505 All fMRI acquisitions were conducted using the 3T Siemens Magnetom® Verio scanner
506 (maximum gradient amplitude of 45 mT/m) located at the imaging platform PIXANIM
507 (Phénotypage par Imagerie in et ex vivo de l'Animal à la Molécule,
508 <https://doi.org/10.17180/CQ4D-DW26>). The sheep were in a prone position, head-first in the
509 MRI scanner. A spherical 24-channel sheep's head coil (diameter: 20 cm; RAPID Biomedical
510 GmbH, Rimpfing, Germany, 1H Phased Array for Sheep Brain P-H24LE-030-01808) was used for
511 all three awake fMRI experiments (BIP, SVL, TOUCH) and for AN-TOUCH, whereas a 4-
512 channel Siemens Large FLEX was used for AN-BIP (Table S02). Functional images covering the
513 whole brain were acquired using a multi-band accelerated echo-planar imaging (EPI) sequence<sup>34-
514 36</sup>. For all experiments, the primary acquisition parameters are described in milliseconds; and a
515 complete description of the acquisition parameters that were used for each sequence for each of
516 the fMRI experiments can be found (in French) in the file "acquisition_parameters.pdf"

517

518 **fMRI Preprocessing**

519 All MRI data processing was conducted using Jupyter Notebooks within the Neurodesk App
520 environment (v2025-04-08)³⁷. DICOM data were converted to NIfTI using dcm2niix (version
521 1.2.20211006)³⁸. The NIfTI files were then organized using the Brain Imaging Data Structure
522 (BIDS v.1.1)³⁹. Preprocessing was performed using a workflow created with Nipype (version
523 1.8.3⁴⁰) that worked as an interface between the various neuroimaging software packages
524 required. For each EPI run:

- 525 1. 4D EPI files were split into 3D using the *TimeSeriesDisassemble* function of the
526 *ImageMath* utility in Advanced Normalisation Tools (ANTs, version 2.3.5)⁴¹.

- 527 2. This enabled the use of the *3dAutomask* function from the AFNI software package
528 (version 23.3.02)⁴² to automatically generate skull-stripped EPI volumes containing only
529 brain tissue voxels.
- 530 3. The mean EPI of the run was generated using the *AverageImages* function from ANTs.
- 531 4. The 3D skull-stripped EPI images were combined into a 4D NIFTI file using
532 *TimeSeriesAssemble* function of the *ImageMath* utility in ANTs.
- 533 5. Each 4D EPI run was then motion corrected using the *antsMotionCorr* function from
534 ANTs by rigidly registering each EPI volume to the mean EPI volume of the run.
- 535 a. A conservative threshold of 2 mm was used to determine whether AN and AW data were
536 included in the analysis; only datasets with less than 2 mm of movement in any of the six rigid-
537 body motion parameters were analyzed. For AW runs with more than 2 mm of motion, the data
538 were cropped to include only the volumes corresponding to the largest number of complete trials
539 unaffected by motion. For example, in an AW run originally containing four trials, if movement
540 exceeding 2 mm occurred during the third trial, the run would be cropped by removing all
541 volumes following the end of the second trial.
- 542 6. The motion corrected files were then slice time corrected to a reference time-point
543 representing half of the repetition time (TR; e.g., to 1 s for a 2 s TR) using 3dTshift from
544 AFNI.
- 545 a. Note that this step was not conducted for AN-BIP-Sparse as it is not appropriate to do
546 slice time correction across the large TR-effective.
- 547 7. The slice time corrected EPI images were then normalised to the Turone Sheep Brain
548 Template and Atlas (TSBTA - <https://zenodo.org/records/10730961>)^{43,44} using
549 *antsRegistration_affine_SyN.sh* ([https://github.com/CoBrALab/minc-toolkit-
550 extras/blob/master/antsRegistration_affine_SyN.sh](https://github.com/CoBrALab/minc-toolkit-extras/blob/master/antsRegistration_affine_SyN.sh)), which implements an optimised
551 diffeomorphic symmetric normalization⁴⁵. This normalization had two purposes: 1) to
552 correct for susceptibility distortion artifacts⁴⁶ and 2) to put the data into a standard space
553 comparable across experiments, sessions, individuals, and runs.
- 554 8. Finally, the normalised EPI images were smoothed to have a Full-Width at Half-
555 Maximum (FWHM) of 3.02mm (2 voxels) using the *3dBlurToFWHM* function from
556 AFNI.

557

558 **fMRI Analysis**

559 First-level (subject-level) fMRI analyses were conducted using a workflow created in Nipype
560 and using SPM12 (Wellcome Centre for Human Neuroimaging, UCL, London, UK)⁴⁷. For each
561 animal, a general linear model (GLM) was specified to model BOLD responses during the
562 experimental conditions⁴⁸. For each run, the blocks of each condition were modeled as a boxcar
563 function representing the duration of each block, convolved with the canonical hemodynamic
564 response function (HRF) provided by SPM. Separate regressors were included for each
565 experimental condition, which depended on the experiment. For *AN-BIP-Continuous*, *AN-BIP-
566 Sparse* and *AW-BIP* two regressors were included: one for the High and one for the Low
567 frequency sounds. For *AW-SVL* three regressors were included: one each for the animal
568 vocalization (NSV), sheep vocalization (SV) and non-vocal environment (NV) sound conditions.
569 For *AN-Touch* and *AW-Touch* two regressors were included: one for the Left and one for the

570 Right side stroking conditions. The six motion parameters obtained during motion correction
571 (three translations and three rotations) were included as nuisance regressors to account for
572 residual head motion. Baseline was not explicitly modelled. A high-pass filter with a cutoff of
573 128 seconds was applied to remove low-frequency drifts, and serial correlations were modeled
574 using an AR(1) process. Parameter estimation was performed using restricted maximum
575 likelihood (ReML). Contrast images were created at the individual animal level and depended on
576 the experiment.

- 577 • *AN-BIP-Continuous & AN-BIP-Sparse & AW-BIP*: To localize the auditory cortex the
578 average BOLD response to sounds (High and Low) was contrasted to the implicit, no-
579 stimulation baseline condition ([0.5, 0.5]; sound > baseline). To investigate the possible
580 tonotopic organization of the auditory cortex the BOLD response to High was contrasted
581 to Low ([1, -1]; High > Low) and Low to High ([-1, 1]; Low > High).
- 582 • *AW-SVL*: To localize the auditory cortex the average BOLD response to sounds
583 (SheepVoice and NonSheepVoice and NonVoc) was contrasted to the implicit, no-
584 stimulation baseline condition ([0.5, 0.5]; sound > baseline). To test for voxels
585 responding preferentially to conspecific sheep vocalizations over all other sounds a
586 conjunction contrast was created: SV > NSV and SV > NV. This combined contrasting
587 the BOLD response to sheep vocalizations to that of non-sheep vocalizations ([1, -1, 0])
588 and to non-vocal environmental sounds ([1, 0, -1]).
- 589 • *AN-Touch & AW-Touch*: To localize the somatosensory cortex the average BOLD
590 response to touch (Left and Right) was contrasted to the implicit baseline condition ([0.5,
591 0.5]; Touch > baseline). To test for contralateral processing, Left touch was contrasted to
592 Right ([1, -1]; Left > Right) as well as Right to Left ([-1, 1]; Right > Left).

593 All statistical analyses were conducted within the whole-brain mask of the TSBTA template. The
594 atlas of the TSBTA was used to anatomically label the significantly activated regions. However,
595 the sylvian gyrus is identified in the TSBTA as a single region. For clarity and consistency with
596 prior work we used the term ectosylvian gyrus for this region and subdivided it into its anterior
597 and posterior parts⁵.

598 All voxels surviving a voxel-wise uncorrected threshold of $p < 0.001$ are reported in the
599 supplementary information (Supplementary Tables 3-81). For each, it is also indicated whether
600 they survive a more stringent voxel-wise uncorrected threshold of $p < 0.0001$ or a Family-Wise
601 Error (FWE) corrected threshold of $p < 0.05$. Results are presented and interpreted at the
602 individual level. For each experiment, whole-brain analysis is first reported with a focus on
603 hypothesized cortical and subcortical regions of interest, followed by other regions consistently
604 observed across individuals and/or experiments. The term “activation” is used throughout as a
605 shortcut to summarizing regions exhibiting statistically significant BOLD responses to sensory
606 stimuli.

607

608 **Extended Data Table 1 | fMRI experimental design**

Experiment	Animal	Sex	Age Month	Total Sessions	Runs per session	Trials per run	Total Trials	Analyzable Trials	Blocks per trial
AN-BIP continuous	03068	F	24-25	2	2	50	200	200	3: High - Low - Baseline
	03686	F	24-25	2	2	50	200	200	
	03111	M	24-25	2	2	50	200	200	
	03067	M	24-25	2	2	50	200	200	
AN-BIP sparse	03068	F	24-25	2	2	50	200	150	3: High - Low - Baseline
	03686	F	24-25	2	2	50	200	200	
	03067	M	24-25	2	2	50	200	200	
	03111	M	24-25	2	2	50	200	100	
AW-BIP	Lily	F	21 - 35	24	1-5	1-5	113	65	3: High - Low - Baseline
	Brook	F	16 - 35	55	1-3	1-8	163	60	
	Maggie	F	16 - 26	33	1-4	1-6	180	60	
	Barnita	F	20 - 25	18	1-3	1-3	66	41	
	Léonard	M	16 - 26	33	1-2	1-8	138	60	
	Ted	M	19 - 23	22	1-2	4-6	133	68	
	Tony	M	16 - 36	32	1-4	1-8	110	27	
AW-SVL	Lily	F	24 - 27	21	1-5	1-2	76	44	4: SheepVoice - NonSheepVoice - NonVoice - Baseline
	Maggie	F	24 - 27	18	1-4	1-3	83	60	
	Barnita	F	25 - 36	46	1-4	1	81	47	
	Léonard	M	23 - 27	16	1-2	1-3	61	50	
	Ted	M	24 - 27	23	1-2	1-3	65	49	
AN-TOUCH 24-CH	B01	F	60	1	2	25	50	50	4: Right, Left, Baseline * 2
	B02	F	60	1	2	25	50	50	
	B03	M	36	1	2	25	50	50	
	B04	M	36	1	2	25	50	50	
AW-TOUCH	Lily	F	30 - 34	26	1-3	1-2	74	51	4: Right, Left, Baseline * 2
	Maggie	F	30 - 34	27	1-3	1-3	67	43	
	Léonard	M	30 - 36	28	1-6	1-2	61	40	
	Ted	M	30 - 36	34	1-6	1-2	81	51	

609 *Age (month)* of each animal at 1st run and at last run for each experiment

610

611

Extended Data Fig. 1 | Illustration of the tactile stimulation procedure

612 **Extended Data Table 2 | fMRI acquisition parameters**

Experiment	Type	Coil	TR (ms)	TE (ms)	MB	Flip Angle (°)	Number slices	Slice thickness (mm)	FOV (mm)	Matrix (Px)	In plane resolution (mm)	iPAT	BW (Hz/Px)	Volumes	Total duration (min:s)
	Continuous		1564											846	22:19
AN-BIP	Sparse	4 channels	1564 +delay in TR = 8846	35	2	80	40	1.51	172 x 172	114 x 114	1.51 x 1.51	2	1186	151	27:56
AW-BIP	Continuous	24 channels	2000	40	2	80	40	1.51	172x172	114 x 114	1.51 x 1.51	2	1186	#	#
AW-SVL	Continuous	24 channels	2000	35	2	80	40	1.51	172x172	114 x 114	1.51 x 1.51	2	1186	#	#
AN-TOUCH	Continuous	24 channels	2000	35	2	80	40	1.51	172x172	114 x 114	1.51 x 1.51	2	1186	406	13:52
AW-TOUCH	Continuous	24 channels	2000	35	2	80	40	1.51	172x172	114 x 114	1.51 x 1.51	2	1186	#	#

613 *MB: Multiband; FOV: Field of view; BW: Bandwidth; Total duration: per run; # indicates a variable number depending on the performance of the*
614 *animals.*

615

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622

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624

625 **Author contributions.** conceptualization: CaP, SAL. Methodology: CaP, SAL, ML, EC, HA,
626 FE, CeP, DD. Investigation: CaP, SAL, DD, CeP, HA, FE. Visualization: CaP, SAL. Funding
627 acquisition: SAL. Project administration: SAL. Supervision: SAL, EC. Writing – original draft:
628 CaP, SAL. Writing – review & editing: CaP, CeP, DD, HA, FE, ML, EC, SAL.

629

630 **Competing interests.** The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

631

632 **Data and materials availability.** The data generated during the current study are available in the
633 associated Zenodo repository (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18156198>).